

1 **An experimental immune activation regimen targeting a receptor activated in liver metastasis,**
2 **Vsig4.**

3 Pre-Clinical/Clinical/Translational/Phase1-3
4 Compassionate Use Document (FDA format)

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1. Metastasis to the liver is most frequent in patients with colorectal cancer¹⁻³.
 2. We mined published and publicly available RNA-sequencing data^{4,5} using only human tumor tissues to compare primary and metastatic tumor transcriptomes for the discovery of genes associated with liver metastasis in human colorectal cancer.
 3. We describe here differential expression of V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4 encoded by VSIG4 in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer.
 4. VSIG4 mRNA was present at increased quantities in liver metastatic tissues as compared to primary colorectal tumors.
 5. Expression of VSIG4 in primary tumors was correlated with patient overall and recurrence-free survival.
 6. Biologically relevant changes in VSIG4 expression may be relevant to the molecular mechanisms underlying metastasis of tumor cells from the colon and rectum to the liver in humans with metastatic colorectal cancer.

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1. Metastasis to the liver occurs in a wide variety of cancers but is most frequent in patients with metastatic colorectal cancer¹⁻³.
 2. We performed comparative transcriptome analysis of primary tumors from the colon and rectum to metastatic tumors from the liver in patients with metastatic colorectal cancer using published RNA-sequencing data⁴.
 3. We utilized a separate RNA-sequencing gene expression dataset⁵ to determine if target differential expression was a shared feature of liver metastasis among patients with colorectal cancer.
 4. We combined target discovery using differential gene expression with study of human survival in colorectal cancer⁶ based on primary tumor gene expression to enhance understanding of metastasis to the liver in human colorectal cancer.

18 **Methods**

20 We used datasets GSE213402⁴ and GSE179979⁵ for this global differential gene expression
21 analysis of liver metastasis in colorectal cancer in conjunction with GEO2R. GSE213402 was generated
22 using Illumina HiSeq 2500 (Homo sapiens) technology with $n=10$ primary colorectal tumors and $n=10$ liver
23 metastases from patients with colorectal cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL16791.
24 GSE56493 was generated using Illumina HiSeq 2500 technology with $n=4$ primary colorectal tumors and
25 $n=3$ liver metastases from patients with colorectal cancer; analysis was performed using platform
26 GPL16791. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p -value adjustment was used for ranking of
27 differential expression but raw p -values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential
28 expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform
annotation was used. For Kaplan-Meier survival analysis, we used the Kaplan-Meier plotter tool⁶ for
correlation of VSIG4 mRNA expression levels with overall survival in $n=1055$ patients with colorectal
cancer and recurrence-free survival in $n=1296$ patients with colorectal cancer.

Results

We performed comparative transcriptome analysis of metastatic tumor tissues from patients with metastatic colorectal cancer using published and publicly available RNA-sequencing data^{4,5} for rapid discovery, validation and clinical translation of novel therapeutic targets.

VSIG4 is differentially expressed in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer.

1. We identified V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4, encoded by VSIG4, as a differentially expressed gene in the liver metastatic tissues of humans with colorectal cancer⁴ (Chart 1).
2. When sorting each of the genes expressed in liver metastases based on significance of difference in expression transcriptome-wide as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, VSIG4 ranked 21 out of 15341 total transcripts (Chart 1), equating to 99.9% differential expression.
3. Differential expression of VSIG4 in the liver metastases of patients with colorectal cancer was statistically significant (Chart 1; $p=7.25E-07$).
4. We interrogated a second whole transcriptome dataset⁵ for target validation, comparing total gene expression between liver metastases and primary tumors of the colon and rectum, again revealing differential expression of VSIG4 in metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer (Chart 2).
5. When sorting each of the genes expressed in liver metastases as compared to primary colorectal tumors, VSIG4 ranked 3619 out of 19486 total transcripts, equating to 81.4% differential expression (Chart 2).
6. Differential expression of VSIG4 in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer trended towards statistical significance (Chart 2; $p=5.30E-02$).
7. Differential expression of VSIG4 in the liver metastases of humans with metastatic colorectal cancer, both identified blindly and through whole transcriptome methodologies, and validated across laboratories, suggested that differential expression of VSIG4 is a transcriptional feature of metastasis to the liver in humans with colorectal cancer, rather than an experimental artifact, a reflection of idiosyncratic behavior in cell culture or animal models, or an observation from a single laboratory.

VSIG4 is expressed at higher levels in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer.

8. We obtained exact mRNA expression levels for VSIG4, in primary tumors of the colon and rectum and in liver metastasis of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer to determine direction and statistical significance of change in VSIG4 expression in liver metastases.
9. VSIG4 was expressed at higher levels in the liver metastases of patients with colorectal cancer as compared to primary colorectal tumors, but this difference was not deemed statistically significant (Figure 1; $p=0.1355$).
10. VSIG4 was expressed at 1.68 ± 1.52 transcripts in primary tumors of the colon and rectum, while it was expressed at 15.29 ± 26.23 transcripts in liver metastasis from patients with colorectal cancer.
11. We calculated a mean fold change of 9.12 in VSIG4 mRNA levels when comparing liver metastases from patients with colorectal cancer and primary tumors of the colon and rectum.

VSIG4 expression is significantly correlated with survival outcomes in human colorectal cancer.

12. We performed Kaplan-Meier survival analysis⁶ to examine relationships between VSIG4 tumor expression and survival outcomes in colorectal cancer.
13. We observed a statistically significant correlation between primary tumor expression of VSIG4 and overall survival (OS) in human colorectal cancer (Figure 2, Chart 3; logrank p -value: 0.0015; hazard ratio: 1.39 (1.13-1.7)).
14. Colorectal cancer patients whose primary tumors expressed low levels of VSIG4 possessed median OS of 134 months, while colorectal cancer patients whose tumors expressed high levels of VSIG4 possessed median OS of 102 months.

1 15. We also observed a statistically significant correlation between primary tumor expression of
2 VSIG4 and recurrence-free survival (RFS) in human colorectal cancer (Figure 2, Chart 4; logrank p -value:
3 0.024; hazard ratio: 1.28 (1.03-1.58)).

4 16. Colorectal cancer patients whose primary tumors expressed low levels of VSIG4 possessed
5 median RFS of 60 months, while colorectal cancer patients whose tumors expressed high levels of VSIG4
6 possessed median RFS of 29.39 months.

7 17. Thus, through blind study and quantitative analysis of published and publicly available
8 RNA-sequencing data^{4,5}, we identified V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4, encoded by VSIG4,
9 as among the genes whose expression was most different, transcriptome-wide, in the liver metastases of
10 patients with metastatic colorectal cancer; VSIG4 messenger RNA was present at higher quantities in
11 metastasis to the liver.

12 18. We observed a correlation between VSIG4 primary tumor expression and patient survival
13 outcomes in human colorectal cancer.

14 Discussion

15 1. We provided evidence here that V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4, encoded by
16 VSIG4, is among the genes whose expression is most different in the liver metastases of patients with
17 metastatic colorectal cancer, that VSIG4 mRNA is present at increased quantities in liver metastatic
18 tissues as compared to primary tumors of the colon and rectum, and that primary tumor VSIG4 expression
19 is significantly correlated with patient survival outcomes in human colorectal cancer.

20 2. First-in-human administration of a Vsig family antibody for immune-mediated control of distant
21 metastasis is merited.

22 3. Modulation of VSIG4 expression may be relevant to the processes by which colorectal cancer
23 cells exit the gastrointestinal tract, migrate the portal vein and colonize the liver.

24 4. This document provides rationale, background, and sufficient data including study of human
25 survival for lengths of time that far surpasses that which normally occurs in a standard clinical trial (greater
26 than 16 years, or 200 months) in patients with CRC strictly based on tumor expression of the specified
27 target of interest, to support Compassionate Use in humans with treatment-resistant metastatic colorectal
28 cancer.

5. The Vsig4 monoclonal antibody is currently under development.

1 **References**

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Rank: 21
p-value: 7.25E-07
stat: -4.9544565
log2FoldChange: -3.76618051
baseMean: 62.23
Gene: VSIG4
Gene name: V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4

Chart 1: VSIG4 is among the genes whose expression is most different across the transcriptome when comparing total gene expression between the liver metastases and primary tumors of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer.

The rank of global differential expression, the *p*-value with respect to differential expression transcriptome-wide, stat (the Wald statistic), fold change in gene expression expressed as log2, basemean, the average of normalized counts among all samples analyzed the gene and gene name are listed in this chart.

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Rank: 3619
p-value: 5.30E-02
stat: -1.9352313
log2FoldChange: -1.8707666
baseMean: 489.47
Gene: VSIG4
Gene name: V-set and immunoglobulin domain-containing 4

Chart 2: VSIG4 is a differentially expressed gene in liver metastatic colorectal cancer.

The rank of global differential expression, the *p*-value with respect to differential expression transcriptome-wide, stat (the Wald statistic), fold change in gene expression expressed as log2, basemean, the average of normalized counts among all samples analyzed the gene and gene name are listed in this chart.

Figure 1: VSIG4 is expressed at higher levels in the liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer when compared to primary colorectal tumors.

The mRNA expression level of VSIG4 in primary tumors of the colon and rectum (left) and in liver metastases of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer (right) is graphically depicted; the result of a statistical test evaluating significance of difference in VSIG4 expression between primary tumors and liver metastases is listed above.

Figure 2: VSIG4 primary tumor expression correlates with overall survival and recurrence-free survival in human colorectal cancer.

Depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots is the probability of overall survival for $n=1055$ patients with colorectal cancer (left), and the probability of recurrence-free survival for $n=1296$ patients with colorectal cancer (right), stratified into two groups, based on low or high expression of VSIG4 in patient primary tumors. The log rank p-value denoting statistical significance of difference in each survival metric when comparing the two groups, as well as hazard ratio for this comparison is listed above. Listed below is the number of patients at risk per interval, after stratification based on VSIG4 expression; in the first interval, number at risk is number of patients alive; in each subsequent interval, number at risk is the number at risk less those who have expired (OS), whose disease has recurred (RFS), or are censored.

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Low VSIG4 expression: 134 months
High VSIG4 expression: 102 months

Chart 3: Median overall survival is superior in colorectal cancer patients with low primary tumor expression of VSIG4.

The median OS of patients with low primary tumor expression of VSIG4 and high primary tumor expression of VSIG4 is listed in this chart, for $n=1055$ colorectal cancer patients.

Low VSIG4 expression: 60 months
High VSIG4 expression: 29.39 months

Chart 4: Median recurrence-free survival is superior in colorectal cancer patients with low primary tumor expression of VSIG4.

The median RFS of patients with low primary tumor expression of VSIG4 and high primary tumor expression of VSIG4 is listed in this chart, for $n=1296$ colorectal cancer patients.